

DIBUJANDO LA POBREZA, COLOREAMOS LA PAZ

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We aim to motivate assistants to question themselves about the connections between poverty and peace in the Colombian context, and what poverty and peace mean to them as individuals and as a group. We feel that if we focus on how poverty and peace feel, the outcomes might be extraordinary.

WORKSHOP POSITION PAPER - BACKGROUND ISSUES

Poverty and inequality figures remain

“Colombia’s social agenda has undergone a dramatic evolution in recent years. The growth and sophistication of public social programs has been accompanied by a deepening of private sector involvement with poverty-related issues. However, poverty and inequality figures remain unacceptably high, and it is now accepted that neither sector’s offer is sufficient to create inclusion and address problems of poverty at the scale that is required. In this context, social innovation has been recognized as a tool that can unlock more effective approaches to issues of poverty, and facilitate the cooperation between actors in various sectors”¹.

The Agency and its Center for Social Innovation have been consistently working on discovering new ways and initiatives to

1 Taken from the Project abstract PIONEROS SYSTEM OF SOCIAL INNOVATION, presented to the Multilateral Investment Fund MINF in 2012, and approved in March 2013. Developed by Compartamos con Colombia in association with Anspe.

solve challenges related to poverty, viewing it from the potential of communities to create better solutions. Simultaneously, Colombia is going through a peace process that is fundamental for overcoming extreme poverty, as overcoming extreme poverty is fundamental for the success of the peace process. We see that people and organizations are talking about poverty and peace, but not experimenting how peace and poverty feel like. No time is being invested in imagining a different reality.

We want to develop a process in which participants can connect to what poverty and peace represent to them, and let them realize that the created process is really conducted by them, although facilitated by an expert.

WORKSHOP POSITION - PAPER- WORKSHOP GOAL

To develop a collective process of creation in which participants will come up with an idea (project) related to poverty and peace, so that it can later be developed by one (or more than one) of the leaders of the workshop.

WORKSHOP POSITION PAPER - APPROACH

Our approach is not theoretical but emotional. This means that the creative process will not be based on concepts or theories but on a set of questions that connect the participants to what they are going to create. In other words, we are going to focus on the “why” and not on the “what”.

NAMES, AFFILIATIONS AND CONTACT INFORMATION

The workshop is led by the Center for Social Innovation (CIS) of The National Agency to Overcome Extreme Poverty in Colombia (ANSPE by its Spanish initials) in collaboration with:

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Number of participants (Attendees): between 15 and 40, ideally.

Duration of the workshop: 6 hours.

Location: Bogotá D.C., Universidad de los Andes.

Target

The workshop is intended for multi-sectorial participants interested in comprehending poverty and peace from a different perspective, and willing to think and create collectively around these matters.

- Students (particularly on the areas of design).
- Professionals.
- Private sector.
- Public sector.
- Academia.
- Community.
- NOG's.

Characteristics of the Space

Taking into account the methodology and activities (collaborative work), the room should ideally have:

- Capacity for 80 people.
- Good illumination (natural light if possible).
- Movable structures (tables, seats)
- Structures that allow facilitators to post light elements so the creative process can be visualized by participants.

Materials and Special Requirements

Round tables seating 8 to 10 people (movable); acrylic boards and erasable markers; 15 to 40 seats (easily movable); post-its; sheets of paper; video beam; sound system.